

PROCESSES OF USING VIRTUAL TOURS AND SMART PROGRAMS IN THE ACTIVITIES OF MUSEUMS OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation: This article talks about virtual tours, smart programs, their use processes, advantages, conveniences of opportunities created on the basis of modern technologies and their organization processes implemented in the museums of Uzbekistan. In the article, the possibilities of virtual tours organized in museums, the issues of development of the field of museology, which are of great importance today, are scientifically highlighted.

Key words: project, virtual museum, 3D format, video film, website, web catalog, multimedia, virtual tour, photorealistic, panorama.

In the development of museums today, the creation of electronic resources is of great importance. And in this regard, museums are establishing cooperation with several leading cultural and historical organizations of the world. Through the introduction of innovative technologies in the museum, international cultural relations are expanding. In this direction, the museum created the project "Samarkand Museum - virtual tour". The project included a virtual form of the Samarkand United Historical-Architectural Art Museum-Reserve and the Museum of Local History of the Samarkand Region and the Afro-Syob Museum. The virtual tour posted on the www.sammuseum.uz page has created convenience for our people and tourists. The virtual tour includes 22 panoramas and about 600 exhibits of the Samarkand United Historical-Architectural Art Museum-Reserve, 18 panoramas and about 700 exhibits of the Afrosiyob Museum, 24 panoramas and more than 200 exhibits of the Museum of Local History of the Samarkand Region. included.

It is now possible to see a virtual demonstration of this museum on Internet sites. Through this website, the viewer can watch the exposition, which reflects the history of the reign of Mirzo Ulugbek, as well as get all the information about the activity of the Mirzo Ulugbek observatory in Samarkand, which was built by oriental scholars in the 15th century. This project was created in 2012 in cooperation with the Samarkand State Museum Reserve and its branch in Samarkand - the Mirzo Ulugbek Museum and the Tashkent company "SMI-Asia". In the creation of the project, a non-profit organization focused on the development and study of modern culture "Desht-i-Art" center laboratory, educational programs within the museum work, as well as the Khivos Foundation (Netherlands) provided great support. The project is available in three languages: Uzbek, Russian and English. It is important to note that this project was included among the first 3D virtual museums of Uzbekistan. The developers presented the virtual museum project on DVDs to secondary and higher education institutions. This will greatly help in making the educational process on this topic more interesting and comprehensive. The employees of the Samarkand museum reserve say that it is even possible to get these discs by visiting the museum.

African murals. Rare examples of this majestic painting have been found as a result of archaeological excavations in Africa. The first samples were discovered by archaeologist V. Vyatkin (1913). During the next period of excavations (1965-68), Uzbek archaeologists managed to open about 30 palace rooms, many of these rooms were decorated with murals and patterns. Of these, the paintings in the large and small rooms are relatively well preserved. In one of the rooms, a man and a woman are depicted sitting in front of an arch. The paintings on the walls of the large room are significant for their richness of details and preserved Sughd inscriptions. The analysis of preserved paintings allows us to think about the ideological artistic direction of medieval majestic fine art, the artist's working methods and tools, detailed household scenes, and ethnic scenes of that period. Afro-siyab wall paintings show the development of majestic painting in Central Asia before the Arab conquest, and Samarkand was its center. A number of scientists are conducting research on African wall paintings. In particular, a large-scale project was carried out to reveal and display history through wall paintings.

In 2014, Uzbek and Korean scientists collaborated to create a 3D video film of "Afro-Siob Wall Paintings". In July 2013, a joint project with the Samarkand United Historical-Architectural Art Museum-Reserve and the Northeast Asian History Foundation (Republic of Korea) on the computer restoration of "Afro-Siyab wall paintings" and the creation of a 3D video film contract was signed. This video is shown in Uzbek, Russian, Korean, English, French languages in the video hall of the museum. The creation of a 3D video film of "Afrosiyob wall paintings" was a big event not only in Samarkand, but also in the cultural life of the republic. Virtual video film is a unique project that meets all the requirements for today's era.

State Museum of Applied Arts of Uzbekistan. Collections, various events, exhibitions and other information are provided in the Internet system. The museum's virtual presentation, i.e., its website, includes a list of the museum's range of services, as well as a brief description of the guided tours and lectures. Not only museums, but also cultural libraries and archives are working on the creation and use of information resources. Currently, various documents and information are stored in museums - card files and catalogs, books and museum collections, dissertations and unique archival documents.

If museums create a modern way of providing information about their collections using electronic documentation and digital image methods, this will give them the opportunity to introduce themselves in the international Internet network. In addition, it is possible to create new Internet resource bases based on the interests of permanent Internet users by collecting their opinion in the museum e-mail. Also, through the combination of images and text in these networks, viewers get acquainted with a continuous new information system related to the topic. The creation of the Web-catalog of museums allows targeted cooperation with other existing museums. In this regard, it is also effective for museums to create websites and national catalogs in harmony with various interesting collections. It is possible to study all the interests and useful information in the Web system, as well as new electronic cataloging and electronic placement of images, through the currently available Web sites. The creation of multimedia products and their use in the museum experience will be interesting and useful for the audience based on the projects presented. The introduction of the culture and history of Uzbekistan through the Internet system within the museum

collection and the creation of modern programs will serve as an important factor in the creation of new innovative aspects of museum activity in the future.

Museums will have the opportunity to create their collections using electronic documentation and digital image methods and modern technical means, and to promote themselves in the international Internet network.

The demonstration of open-air museums, which is one of the main links of Uzbekistan's tourism, through advanced Internet technologies, will increase the number of tourists and interest in historical heritage. Convenience in searching for the necessary information on the Internet, that is, information about the desired city or historical monuments of interest to tourists, the creation of new compact wireless transmission equipment and devices that allow fast connection to the network, the expansion of the volume of information related to tourist trips and the improvement of the quality of tourism. is the basis for creating an idea about the big prospects of business and e-commerce. The number of users of Internet services in the field of tourism is increasing rapidly. Because new telecommunication systems allow consumers to plan their travel program independently and in convenient conditions, determine the duration of the trip, and order tickets accordingly. Such innovative processes fully correspond to the content of the policy carried out by the government in the country. The worthy participation of our country in various prestigious fairs, conferences and events in the field allows us to demonstrate our potential in the field of tourism in international markets and attract additional tourists. Tourism development requires close communication and relations with international tourism organizations. The creation of virtual views of open-air museums is of great importance in this regard. International tourist fairs are held in Tashkent every year. The leadership of World Tourist Organizations paid special attention to this. At the international fair, national tourist products and services are brought to the public's attention. These include colorful stands of different cities, photos showing the attractiveness of our country in all seasons. At such fairs, it is appropriate to show virtual views of our ancient monuments through various multimedia programs, to provide more information about their history. This will increase the attention and interest of tourists to our historical heritage. Currently, various tourist companies in our country have their own websites. The pages contain information about noteworthy places of Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, work has been carried out in the field of virtual panorama (3D panorama or spherical panorama). That is, it is a photorealistic representation of a large area. A panorama of 3D images appears on the monitor screen. 3D panorama allows us to see 360 degrees and vertically.

By watching a virtual 3D panorama, the viewer gets more information visually than by looking at a regular photo. With the help of a computer button, it is possible to look around, zoom in or out of the object of interest at will. Such an interactive virtual 3D panorama enhances the visitor's impression. In the virtual panorama, the historical monuments of Samarkand, Bukhara, Shahrisabz, Tashkent, as well as modern buildings, peaceful places and statues of Uzbekistan are shown. This is from the Panoramio.uz page on the Internet. Panoramio.uz is the first virtual world project in Uzbekistan. The page is comprehensive, it has the opportunity to make virtual trips to various hotels, educational institutions and different parts of our country.

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